

MORPHOLOGICAL AND MICROCIRCULATORY FEATURES OF POST-BURN SCAR DEFORMITIES OF THE FACE AND NECK IN CHILDREN

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Abstract. *To study the morphological, histological, and microcirculatory characteristics of scar tissue in children with post-burn deformities of the face and neck. A comprehensive examination of 108 patients was conducted using histological methods, ultrasound examination, laser Doppler flowmetry (LDF), and fluorescent diagnostics. Clear differential signs of various scar types were established, and criteria for optimizing treatment tactics were proposed. The study results allow for a more accurate determination of the nature of scar tissue and the individualization of treatment approaches.*

Keywords: *scar, burn, hypertrophic scar, keloid, diagnosis, children, face, neck, fluorescence, LDF.*

Introduction.

Post-burn scars, especially in the facial and neck areas in children, represent not only a medical but also a socio-psychological problem. These scars can cause significant functional and aesthetic disorders, contribute to the formation of complexes, social isolation, reduced quality of life, and even the development of psycho-emotional disorders. Considering the anatomical and physiological characteristics of childhood, the tendency to hypertrophic and keloid scarring in this localization is higher than in adults.

Despite the availability of numerous methods for treating post-burn scars, their effectiveness remains limited due to difficulties in accurately diagnosing the type of scar tissue and predicting its further behavior. Morphological and microcirculatory changes in tissues determine the nature of the scar, its response to therapy, and the risk of recurrence. However, in clinical practice, there is still a lack of clear differentiated diagnostic criteria that allow for an individualized approach to treatment.

In this regard, a comprehensive study of the morphological, ultrasound, and fluorescent characteristics of scars becomes particularly relevant, allowing for timely determination of the type of scar tissue, selection of the most effective treatment tactics, and improvement of cosmetic and functional outcomes of surgical correction.

Objective of the Study. To assess the morphological and microcirculatory features of post-burn scars of the face and neck in children to develop differentiated diagnostic criteria aimed at individualizing the treatment approach.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted at the Tashkent Medical Academy and Shoh International Hospital from December 2021 to June 2023. The study included 108 patients aged 2 to 18 years

with post-burn scar deformities of the face and neck. The control group consisted of 30 patients who underwent treatment in other clinics of the republic according to traditional schemes.

Inclusion Criteria:

Presence of a post-burn scar in the facial or neck area.

Age from 2 to 18 years.

Absence of acute inflammatory diseases at the time of examination.

Diagnostic Methods:

Histological examination of scar tissue biopsies to assess cellular composition, degree of fibrosis, and vascular features.

Ultrasound examination (US) to assess the thickness and echostructure of the scar, visualization of deep changes.

Laser Doppler flowmetry (LDF) for quantitative assessment of regional microcirculation in the scar area.

Fluorescent diagnostics to determine tissue activity based on the degree of photosensitizer accumulation and fluorescence intensity.

Clinical Assessment:

Vancouver Scar Scale (VSS).

Patient and Observer Scar Assessment Scale (POSAS).

DN4 and 4-D questionnaires for assessing pain and itching.

Statistical analysis was performed using variation statistics methods: calculation of the mean value (M), standard deviation (σ), and the significance of differences between groups was determined using the Student's t-test ($p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant).

Results

As a result of a comprehensive examination of 108 patients with post-burn scars of the face and neck, characteristic morphological, ultrasound, and microcirculatory features distinguishing various types of scar tissue were identified.

Distribution of Patients by Scar Type:

Hypertrophic scars – 53.8% (n=42).

Keloid scars – 28.2% (n=22).

Contractures – 16.7% (n=13).

Atrophic scars – 1.3% (n=1).

Most patients had multiple scar lesions (61.5%) and regional spread of scar tissue (74.4%).

Histological Analysis:

Hypertrophic scars were characterized by a whorled arrangement of collagen fibers, active proliferation of fibroblasts, pronounced vascularization, edema, and inflammatory elements.

Keloid scars contained dense nodules of amorphous collagen, an increased number of fibroblasts (8 times more than in normal healing), enhanced synthesis of mucopolysaccharides, and signs of lack of self-regression.

Atrophic and normotrophic scars had a thin fibrous structure, reduced density of collagen bundles, and limited vascularization.

Ultrasound Examination:

In patients with keloid scars, US revealed the absence of a clear boundary between scar and healthy tissue, decreased overall echogenicity, presence of hypoechoic zones, and single vascular signals.

Hypertrophic scars had a more pronounced capsule, moderate decrease in echogenicity, and clear boundaries.

Scar thickness ranged from 2 to 10 mm, averaging 4.6 ± 1.3 mm.

Laser Doppler Flowmetry (LDF):

Showed a significant increase in microcirculatory activity in the early stages after injury, especially in hypertrophic scars.

After 6 months, a decrease in blood flow intensity was observed, particularly in areas of dense fibrous tissue.

Fluorescent Diagnostics:

Demonstrated high sensitivity in detecting active zones of pathological scarring.

Hypertrophic and keloid scars exhibited bright, diffuse fluorescence, indicating active metabolism and possible ongoing inflammation.

Normotrophic scars showed weak fluorescence.

Clinical Assessment:

According to the Vancouver Scar Scale (VSS), the average score in the main patient group was 8.7 ± 1.9 compared to 11.2 ± 2.3 in the control group ($p < 0.05$), indicating less pronounced pathological changes with an individualized approach.

Discussion

The results of this study confirm that the nature of morphological and microcirculatory changes in post-burn scar tissue directly affects the clinical course of the disease and the effectiveness of therapeutic measures. The identified features of various scar types allowed for the refinement of differential diagnostic criteria and the proposal of a justified approach to the choice of therapy methods.

Histological analysis showed that hypertrophic and keloid scars are characterized by pronounced fibroblast proliferation, disorganization of collagen fibers, and increased vascular permeability, indicating an active pathological process. These data are confirmed by the results of laser Doppler flowmetry, which recorded high microcirculatory activity in scar zones. Fluorescent diagnostics demonstrated high sensitivity in detecting active metabolic activity in scar tissue, making it a valuable method for early control of treatment effectiveness.

Ultrasound examination confirmed differences in the structure and thickness of scars, which is especially valuable in the differential diagnosis of keloid and hypertrophic scars, as well as in dynamic monitoring of tissue condition.

Comparison with the control group showed that the use of an individualized approach to diagnosis led to a more significant reduction in the severity of scar changes according to VSS and POSAS data. This indicates the feasibility of introducing a morphologically and fluorescently oriented treatment strategy into clinical practice.

Thus, the study data confirm the importance of a comprehensive assessment of scar tissue condition when planning surgical and conservative treatment. This is especially relevant for the localization of scars in the facial and neck areas in children, where not only functional restoration but also achieving the most aesthetic result is required.

Conclusions

Post-burn scars of the face and neck in children are characterized by pronounced morphological diversity, requiring an individualized approach to their diagnosis and treatment.

Histological examination allows for accurate determination of the scar type and the degree of fibrotic changes, especially in differentiating hypertrophic and keloid scars.

Fluorescent diagnostics demonstrated high sensitivity to active zones of pathological scarring and can be recommended for non-invasive monitoring of treatment dynamics.

Laser Doppler flowmetry and ultrasound examination are informative methods for assessing microcirculation and scar tissue structure, enhancing the accuracy of diagnosis and disease course prediction.

The use of comprehensive morphofunctional diagnostics allows for the individualization of treatment tactics for

REFERENCES

1. Alekseev A.A. Modern approaches to the treatment of post-burn scars. *Vestnik Khirurgii*. 2016;175(5):45–50.
2. Belousov A.E., Grishkevich V.M. Morphology and classification of skin scars. *Plastic Surgery and Cosmetology*. 2012;(3):18–23.
3. Vorobyev A.I. Combined methods of treating hypertrophic scars. *Surgery*. 2020;(6):72–76.
4. Gelfand V.B. *Scar deformities: Clinic and treatment*. Moscow: Medicina; 2017. 192 p.
5. Yudenich V.V. Scar changes of the skin of the face and neck in children. *Russian Pediatrics*. 2015;88(2):63–67.
6. Karapetyan G.E., et al. Laser therapy in the treatment of post-burn scars. *Russian Journal of Dermatology and Venereology*. 2013;(1):45–49.
7. Konovalskaya S.B. Integrated approach to the treatment of keloid scars in children. *Pediatric Surgery*. 2003;(4):21–25.
8. Klyuchareva S.V., Nechaeva O.S., Kurganskaya I.G. Use of photodynamic therapy in pathological scars. *Medical Visualization*. 2009;(3):31–36.
9. Liu W., Wang D., Liu Y. Intralesional 5-FU and triamcinolone for hypertrophic scars and keloids: a randomized controlled trial. *Dermatologic Surgery*. 2016;42(9):1047–1055.
10. Tyack Z., Simons M., Wasiak J. A systematic review of burn scar assessment scales. *Burns*. 2012;38(1):6–18. doi:10.1016/j.burns.2011.09.021.
11. World Health Organization (WHO). *Burns – Fact Sheet*. 2021. Available at: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/burns>
12. Resnik S.S., Goodgold J. Hypertrophic Scars and Keloids: Pathophysiology and Clinical Management. *Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery*. 2018;141(3):587e–597e.